

Exercise 2: Reproduce experimental results from a paper

Learning Points and Routes to Recommend Trajectories

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of this paper is to reproduce and evaluate the reproducibility of the [work](#) of Dawei Chen, Cheng Soon Ong and Lexing Xie. This paper was presented in CIKM '16: Proceedings of the 25th ACM International on Conference on Information and Knowledge Management.

KEYWORDS

Trajectory recommendation; learning to rank, planning; reproducibility, experiment design

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1 Introduction

We have tried to fully reproduce the experiment following the paper [1] and code available on Github[4] by using the [data](#) provided.

The purpose of this paper is to recommend a travel path in cities by implementing multiple approaches described in paper and compare them among themselves by measuring F1 and pairs-F1 score. All implemented approaches outperform the random baseline algorithm in both metrics.

In the first step, we analyzed the paper, it's goals, theoretical background, inputs and the results of the experiment. Then we went through the code available in the Github repository [4]. Finally we attempted to reproduce the results by executing the code and trying to figure out the correct configuration of our environment.

The last chapter covers significance testing of conclusions drawn by authors of the paper[1].

2 Data

For the purposes of this report, we used the data available on Github. There are 2 types of data - points of interest (POI) and trajectory (TRAJ). There is a pair of POI and TRAJ dataset for each of the 5 cities : Edinburgh, Glasgow, Melbourne, Osaka and Toronto.

2.1 Data Origin

In the paper [1], authors described how they obtained the datasets by providing citations to other papers, which are supposed to bring more information on datasets. We have checked these papers, but we were unable to find more information about the data origin.

2.2 Metadata

However, the paper doesn't include any specifics about the data. There are only 5 POI and 5 TRAJ csv files. The size of POI datasets is 12 KB and the size of TRAJ datasets is 1304 KB.

3 Data Preparation & Processing

The data preparation is done directly in the source code of the experiment. Generally the process is well documented in the code, the steps included are: extracting trajectories (aggregation of user's journey to a single record), computation of distances between POIs, creation of query tuples (start point, end point, route length), one hot encoding of the categorical features, log scaling of some numerical features, k-means clustering of the pois in order to create a neighborhood attribute etc..

4 Reproducibility

4.1 Execution problems

For reproduction we used the code from Github [4]. The experiment is split into 2 relatively well commented Python Jupyter notebooks. The larger one - "rank_markov.ipynb" loads the data, preprocesses it, creates the "models" and makes predictions and saves the results into files. The notebook needs to be executed for each dataset separately by setting the dataset index in one of the cells.

The other notebook "parse_results.ipynb" is used to load the results for all datasets jointly, calculates the 2 metrics considered in the paper and creates the resulting tables in the same way as they are shown in the paper. The original results produced by "rank_markov.ipynb" were also available in the provided Github[4], when calculating the metrics based on these results we obtained identical tables as in the paper.

As there is no information about version of Python, versions of libraries or the operating system used there were some issues when we tried to execute the code.

For "parse_results.ipynb" there was a compile error in Cython "Cannot assign type 'double' to 'int'" which was possible in the older versions. We solved this by changing the division to integer division (`/` to `//` in the code) which we believe was the intended behaviour.

For the other notebook "rank_markov.ipynb" there were more technical difficulties we came upon. Some of the Pandas library methods such as `set_value` and `get_value` were used but are not available in current Pandas versions, so we replaced them by corresponding methods with the same functionality. Similarly as in the other notebook there was the same Cython error which we solved in the same way. We have had quite some trouble with setting up the Pulp library. The method used in the code was not available in the current version which we installed. As there is not much information about this library it was unclear which version would likely work. We have tried several older versions approximately from around the time when the paper was released, unfortunately we have not managed to make this function in the original way. The older library version also required a binary file to be supplied which was unclear where it should be downloaded from (no information in the paper code/ library documentation). As a workaround we used the up to date version of the library and used the same solver as is demonstrated in the current documentation of the library.

Also as the original experiment was most likely executed on a Linux operating system we needed to change the file paths and file names accordingly for the Windows operating system.

We mentioned the final versions of the libraries we used in the Jupyter Notebook. The code with the adjustments we made can be also found on Github [6].

4.2 Runtime problems

The experiment was executed on 5 different datasets of different sizes from different cities. We only managed to run 3 of them, the computations for the largest ones were stopped after approximately 17 hours (executed on Windows 10 Pro with Intel i7 9700F).

4.3 Reproduced results

The following reproduced tables correspond to the tables in the original paper. As we have previously explained, due to computational reasons it was not possible to calculate the results for all of the datasets.

Table 1: Table corresponding to the table 3 from the original paper. Performance comparison on 3 datasets in terms of F_1 scores. The best method for each dataset (i.e., a column) is shown in bold, the second best is shown in italic.

	Glasgow	Osaka	Toronto
RANDOM	0.632 ± 0.108	0.618 ± 0.129	0.605 ± 0.118
PERS TOUR	0.801 ± 0.213	0.686 ± 0.231	0.720 ± 0.215
PERS TOUR-L	0.660 ± 0.102	0.686 ± 0.137	0.643 ± 0.113
POI POPULARITY	<i>0.745 ± 0.166</i>	0.663 ± 0.125	0.678 ± 0.121
POI RANK	0.679 ± 0.123	0.640 ± 0.135	0.600 ± 0.106
MARKOV	0.722 ± 0.165	0.697 ± 0.150	0.669 ± 0.151
MARKOV PATH	0.735 ± 0.170	0.706 ± 0.150	<i>0.689 ± 0.139</i>
RANK+MARKOV	0.722 ± 0.165	0.697 ± 0.150	0.669 ± 0.151
RANK+MARKOV PATH	0.735 ± 0.170	<i>0.706 ± 0.150</i>	0.689 ± 0.139

Table 2: Table corresponding to the table 4 from the original paper. Performance comparison on 3 datasets in terms of pairs- F_1 scores. The best method for each dataset (i.e., a column) is shown in bold, the second best is shown in italic.

	Glasgow	Osaka	Toronto
RANDOM	0.316 ± 0.144	0.305 ± 0.172	0.286 ± 0.132
PERS TOUR	0.643 ± 0.366	0.468 ± 0.376	0.504 ± 0.354
PERS TOUR-L	0.352 ± 0.162	0.406 ± 0.238	0.333 ± 0.163
POI POPULARITY	<i>0.507 ± 0.298</i>	0.365 ± 0.190	0.384 ± 0.201
POI RANK	0.385 ± 0.205	0.338 ± 0.197	0.276 ± 0.107
MARKOV	0.489 ± 0.293	<i>0.445 ± 0.266</i>	<i>0.407 ± 0.241</i>
MARKOV PATH	0.491 ± 0.297	0.442 ± 0.260	0.406 ± 0.231
RANK+MARKOV	0.489 ± 0.293	0.445 ± 0.266	0.407 ± 0.241
RANK+MARKOV PATH	0.491 ± 0.297	0.442 ± 0.260	0.406 ± 0.231

As we can see from the reproduced results, they slightly differ from the results presented in the original paper. In some cases this caused that different approach is the best performing one in some cases. We believe this might have been caused by different versions of the libraries used, different Python version and different operating system used to execute the experiment. Other than that, there should not be any difference in the execution since the data was provided directly in the code repository, the data preprocessing was also included directly in the code and

the random seeds were properly set in the code. For the significance testing we use the reproduced results.

5 Experiment design flaws

Other than missing details about the libraries, Python versions and operating system used there we have not noticed any major flaws except missing statistical significance testing which we did in 5.1.

5.1 Missing statistical significance testing

The major flaw of the paper is that there is no statistical significance testing to support the conclusions. We have implemented one tailed Welch's t-test using `scipy.stats.ttest_ind_from_stats` to test the conclusions drawn in the original paper. We also double checked the results produced by this library by using `omnicalculator` - they were identical. The statistical significance testing can be found at the end of the "parse_results.ipynb" notebook[6].

In the paper, Authors stated following facts about their achieved performance:

1. All algorithms outperformed random method
2. PoiPopularity outperformed PoiRank
3. Rank+Markov outperformed Markov
4. Rank+MarkovPath outperformed MarkovPath
5. PersTour outperformed PersTour-L

We considered these facts as our hypotheses and ran t-tests to either accept or reject them. The results are shown in the following tables. It is very important to clarify the structure of the tables - Each table represents statistical significance testing for the corresponding hypothesis. Columns represent the data set + method we are comparing. The values in cells are the resulting p-value obtained by running one-tail two sample t-test.

Table 3: Significance values for Welch's t-test which tests whether PersTour outperformed PersTour-L significantly for different datasets

	Glasgow	Osaka	Toronto
PersTour-L	0	0.9991	0

Table 4: Significance values for Welch's t-test which tests whether Rank+MarkovPath outperformed MarkovPath significantly for different datasets

	Glasgow	Osaka	Toronto
MarkovPath	1	1	0.9944

Table 5: Significance values for Welch's t-test which tests whether PoiPopularity outperformed PoiRank significantly for different datasets

	Glasgow	Osaka	Toronto
PoiRank	0.001	0.3858	0

Table 6: Significance values for Welch's t-test which tests whether Rank+Markov outperformed Markov significantly for different datasets

	Glasgow	Osaka	Toronto
Markov	1	1	1

Table 7: Significance values for Welch's t-test which tests whether the algorithms mentioned outperform Random significantly for different datasets

	Glasgow	Osaka	Toronto
PersTour	0	0.0797	0
PersTour-L	0.044	0.0143	0
PoiPopularity	0	0.0861	0
PoiRank	0.0025	0.4219	0.5404
Markov	0	0.007	0
MarkovPath	0	0.003	0
Rank+Markov	0	0.007	0
Rank+MarkovPath	0	0.003	0

6 Conclusion

In general, we consider this paper and its code relatively well documented. We were able to understand relatively quickly, what is the goal of the paper, what is the code used for and how to work with the code. Unfortunately, missing information about the environment specifications caused a lot of trouble. We assume that the older the paper gets, the harder it will be to reproduce and it will be very unlikely to obtain the same results as authors or us.

Another flaw of this paper is missing significance testing which we did in 5.1. By choosing significance value alpha 0.05, we can see that many of the claims from the original paper are not significant according to our testing.

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